

COLLABORATION FOR TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION: CHOICES AND DECISIONS THAT MAKE PARTNERSHIPS EXCEL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to understand the relationship between strategies and collaborative organizational arrangements and the defining of their position within the corporate power structure. The strategic approach employed herein is that of case studies so as to comprehend the peculiarities and the value proposition of the management model of innovation networks at a Brazilian company that operates in the personal hygiene, perfumery and cosmetics segment. To excel within an environment marked by increased global competition, companies have to develop and learn with an innovative work structure and culture. This derives from the rapid shortening of product life cycles which drives the need to innovate at more frequent intervals and to develop technologies, processes, products and/or services more efficiently. Furthermore, given increased product, technologies and processes complexity, attention is drawn to the expansion of costs and risks to innovate to the extent of enhancing uncertainties and pressure on R&D+i (Research,

Development and Innovation) budgets. Meanwhile, the need for interdisciplinarity by means of cooperation likewise comes to light.

Keywords: Technological collaboration. Innovation networks. Partnership management. Strategy and structure. Governance.

COLABORAÇÃO PARA INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA: ESCOLHAS E DECISÕES QUE FAZEM A PARCERIA FUNCIONAR

RESUMO

Neste artigo, o objetivo é compreender a relação entre estratégias e formas organizacionais colaborativas para inovação e a definição de sua posição na estrutura de poder da empresa. Será utilizada a estratégia de estudo de caso para compreender as especificidades e a proposta de valor do modelo de gestão de redes de inovação de uma empresa brasileira do setor de higiene pessoal, perfumaria e cosméticos. Para alcançarem êxito, num ambiente marcado pelo aumento da competição global, as empresas necessitam desenvolver e aprender com uma estrutura e uma cultura de trabalho inovadoras. Isso porque, com o encurtamento veloz do ciclo de vida dos produtos, haveria necessidade de inovar com maior periodicidade e de desenvolver tecnologias, processos, produtos e/ou serviços de forma mais eficiente. Ademais, dado o aumento da complexidade de produtos, tecnologias e processos, observa-se uma expansão dos custos e dos riscos para inovar, elevando a incerteza e as pressões sobre o orçamento de P&D+i (Pesquisa, Desenvolvimento e Inovação). Ao mesmo tempo em que se verifica a necessidade da interdisciplinaridade por meio da cooperação.

Palavras-chave: Colaboração tecnológica. Redes de inovação. Gestão de parcerias. Estratégia e estrutura. Governança.

1. INTRODUCTION

Why do companies collaborate? How can one identify, qualify and select potential partners so as to engage in collaborative activities? What are the skills that one requires “to” and “how to” negotiate and transfer knowledge that is relevant to the innovative process? What are the core elements to ensure an alliance (collaboration) between a given company and it(s) partner(s) excels? What are the elements one finds embedded within a relationship that may drive an alliance (collaboration) between partners towards failure? How should external partners for innovation purposes be managed? (Chatterji, 1996; Chesbrough, 2007, 2012a, 2012b; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Bueno & Balestrin, 2012).

During the 90’s relevant studies in the field of technology management were conducted in Brazil. One of the country’s pioneer studies, coordinated by Vasconcellos (1992), referred to the significance of technology management as an instrument to leverage corporate competitiveness. It was this group of authors’ understanding that technology represented a core tool for competitive efforts in as much as it conditioned the launching of new products and services, in addition with the improvement of those then existing. The study’s focus thus lay in the management of this specific process (technology) and in R&D (Research and Development). Authors further advocated that there was no point in merely hiring specialists and investing in technological development but rather, scarce resources allocated to R&D were to mandatorily be adequately managed (Vasconcellos, 1992). These authors were primarily concerned with the organization and management of R&D as a corporate function, structured in an independent manner before others (e.g.: production, marketing, provisioning, etc.) despite holding relevant interfaces with the same (Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013; Quadros & Vieira, 2008).

Throughout almost the entire 80’s and 90’s, this conceptual model held fast as a reference in Brazil. It was only as of the years 2000 that discussions as to the importance of managing innovation emerged as a field merging and superseding technology or P&D management (Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008). This shift primarily

came about driven by the perception that technological innovation cuts the edge not as a process of mere technical nature, but rather shaped into one whose core result is of a business and economic nature. According to Quadros and Vilha (2006), the quest via technological innovation is one of applying both corporate technological and market-related skills and knowledge and those of its partners, to generate new products, processes, services and businesses (Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2013; Quadros & Vieira, 2008).

Therefore, throughout the mentioned decade, one clearly identifies an inflection in the methodological analytical axis treating the management of processes that handle knowledge, technology and innovation. Theoretical vision, conceptual approaches and formulation of innovation process and its management indicators thus become systematically more systemic and extensive in scope (Quadros & Vieira, 2010; Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2013).

An important element in literature covering the management of science, technology and innovation is that pertaining to the contribution external sources of knowledge offer to innovation or innovation networks (at industrial and service provisioning companies) and, over the past 20 years, it has attracted gradual theoretical and methodological progress. According to Quadros (2008), the volume of research featuring an approach centred on studying the dissemination of innovation network management practices remains bleak despite the same being acknowledged as a distinctive characteristic of innovation considering current competitive conditions (Nooteboom, 2004; Chesbrough, 2007, 2012a, 2012b; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008). Likewise, few are the companies that adopt a systemized and coherent standing to manage their external sources of innovation- whether in as much as the adoption of routines to prospect and select sources and partnerships or as to the design and management of partnerships contracts is concerned (Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2013; Quadros & Vieira, 2008).

One of this paper's differentials rests in the treatment of such external sources (or innovation networks - ground on strategic alignment, partnership integration and inter-organizational collaboration relationship management - as one of innovation strategy's and that of the company's global strategy, key elements.

From this standpoint, technological innovation far beyond being a process of mere technical nature, arises as an uncertain, risky and complex social process

ground on learning and knowledge (internal and external to the company), in the development of core competencies (Prahalad & Hamel, 1997) and in the integration and engagement of multiple players: within and beyond corporate frontiers (Lazonick, 2005; Pavitt, 2005). Multi-faceted processes of the kind – which call for learning, control and continuous improvement – involve negotiation and strategic and managerial choices (decisions amongst alternatives) in addition to behavioral patterns (routines) that likewise ought to be learnt, integrated, internalized and reinforced (Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008) to the extent that, once automated and incorporated into a company's collaborator's day to day activities (and that of its external partners) the same shape into a sort of corporate second nature (Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013; Quadros & Vieira, 2008).

Innovation is a process that comprises the company's whole. As grounding leveraging sustainable competitive advantage, assumptions rest in serious and effective upper management effort and in the allocation of resources that reflect the priority set for innovation; the preparation of tailored processes and tools to manage innovation, executed by those functional areas involved in the same; corporate ability to organize itself to explore its resources and capabilities (valuable, rare and barely imitable), in addition to exploring effective project management; and the managerial and technical staff's entrepreneurial and leadership competencies (Barney & Hesterly, 2008; Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013).

It is Barney and Hesterly's (2008) and also that of Carvalho, Santos and Barros Neto (2011, 2013) understanding that the essence of managing the innovation process consists in the mobilization and coordination of resources/capabilities (financial, physical, human and organizational) and of the company's internal players in addition to those resources/capabilities and of players that lie beyond corporate frontiers (clients, suppliers, research institutions, development, funding and fostering institutions), to nullify threats and foremost, explore opportunities deemed aligned with the company's strategic priorities.

Innovation strategic management seeks to structure - from a strategic standpoint (i.e., with views to obtaining sustainable competitive advantage) – processes, routines, tools, resources/capabilities and organizational practices, in a systemic manner. The purpose of coordinated actions of the kind is to ensure

innovation becomes a periodic, systematic and disciplined process and not something that arises within the company in a spontaneous or accidental manner. Nevertheless, there are no ready-made formulas to neither generate innovation nor manage its process. The innovation manager's demands/needs are specific to each corporate environment as one seeks to align these with the existing strategy, organizational structure, positioning, resources and capabilities, economic segment and overall size. To this effect, companies tailor the management of their innovative processes according to resources and their own priorities since, given peculiarities, hinder managerial options (Quadros & Vilha, 2006; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013).

Given the above, which strategies, routines and organizational arrangements (based on technological cooperation and in the strengthening of the university-corporate interaction) might come to be employed by a Brazilian company, such as Natura, with views to encouraging and facilitating technological innovation? How does this function and how does the standing of these arrangements within the company's power structure shape? What are the corporate impacts that arise from R&D+i (Research, Development and Innovation) projects undertaken in collaboration with Brazilian research groups in the form of Science and Technology Institutions (ICTs)? These are the research queries herein presented.

So as to address the aforementioned questions, research shall attempt to investigate how the company sought to acquire distinctive competencies to innovate in cosmetics (a highly competitive, quality and innovative product demanding market) and how technological collaboration contributed with the attaining of such competencies.

Analysis of information may prove to be of use to inspire the implementation of a collaborative process at other consumer goods centered companies in Brazil. Moreover, it is deemed of strategic value to understand how companies have behaved in terms of organizational arrangement "to the effect of" and "for" innovative process purposes; of the involvement of internal and external partners in the articulation and integration of knowledge and learning for innovation purposes; and how companies seek their technological qualification and connect themselves to external partner networks. All of this not only so as to comprehend the internal dynamic of organizations – namely, how companies with diverse structural

arrangements vary their learning and knowledge creation patterns to generate different kinds of innovative capabilities (Lam, 2005) – but rather also given the respective implications in terms of requirements for the structuring of technological innovation devoted policies and instruments (industrial, educational, scientific, technological, etc.).

2. THE RELEVANCE OF MANAGING EXTERNAL INNOVATION SOURCES AND THE STRATEGIC SEARCH FOR EXTERNAL PARTNERSHIPS

There are some companies that are negatively impacted by the inadequate ability to identify and manage external sources of knowledge and innovation – a core process for their businesses – primarily in as much as their sources may complement and contribute to strengthen their innovation processes (Chatterji, 1996; Chesbrough, 2007, 2012a, 2012b; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Bueno & Balestrin, 2012). Issues of the kind have driven managers to question: how to identify and select partners for collaboration purposes and how one ought to manage the bonds between the same? How to adequately deal with the intrinsic heterogeneity of external innovation partners in such a manner that one comprises competitors, goods and services provisioning companies, clients and research partners at public institutions? What is the effective contribution external partners offer to the company's innovation process effectiveness?

Innovation surveys conducted in Europe, the US and in Brazil over the past couple of decades such as the CIS (*Community Innovation Survey* – European Commonwealth innovation research) and Pintec (conducted by the Brazilian Geography and Statistics Institute - *IBGE*), have supported the comprehensive understanding of requirements, restrictions and determining factors that influence the contribution external sources offer to corporate innovation processes, especially in as much as research sources such as universities and public research laboratories are concerned. The most relevant finding of these surveys possibly refers to the ability to find and select innovation partners depending on the building of internal technological capabilities. The underlying reason resides in the fact that

technological innovation relevant knowledge is specific to the segment, to the company and only the company that is the directly interested party is in a true position to choose amongst alternatives. The knowledge the company has gathered over the years is solid ground to sustain an organized and focused search and selection process. Furthermore, this kind of knowledge is a pre-requisite for learning during the course of interaction with the external partner.

Literature investigating these innovation surveys has also unveiled structural determinants and conditioning factors that would impact the quality and intensity of bonds between companies and universities. Amongst such factors, the size and age of firms, the peculiarities of the business segment, the nature of the innovation process, the field of science involved, regional differences within a given country and the historic evolution of higher education institutions are worthy of special mention (Suzigan, Albuquerque & Cario, 2011). In as much as the Carnegie Mellon Survey is concerned for instance, Cohen, Nelson and Walsh (2002) suggest that public research is crucial to industrial research at given segments, particularly when it comes to advances in sciences such as biology and physics. The study also demonstrated that, instead of outsourcing research to generate new ideas for innovation purposes, companies are more inclined to resort to supplement their capabilities and knowledge in projects in course or to solve technological issues.

To this effect, Santoro and Chakrabarti (2002) perceive a distinct partition between the large and the small company given that the latter's eagerness to find solutions to its crucial problems instead of, in the long run, attempting to build supplementary capabilities in fields that are not as yet deemed essential. Cohen et al. (2002) likewise presented evidence suggesting that although large companies are all in all more inclined than smaller ones to make use of public research, these institutions are far more important for the development of starting-up science-intensive companies.

Nevertheless, the aforementioned studies are limited given the fact that they solely focus on the company's structural aspects, setting the central issue involving strategic and managerial choices aside. Laursen and Salter (2004) suggest that despite structural aspects such as the company's size and age playing a major role in the determining of the inclination to seek relationships with universities, decisions

of the kind are also conditioned by strategic choices as to how one ought to manage corporate innovation-related activities.

Although an increasing number of large companies are boosting their innovation networking and external connection processes with universities and public research institutes, most do not adopt systematic practices to manage these links. Approach is still rather informal, imitative and empiric (Linder, Jarvenpaa & Davenport, 2003). Nevertheless, the systematization of practices that comprise the identification, selection, follow-up and assessment of external research bonds are critical not only to ensure that the best choices amongst alternatives are made but also, the much wanted integration of research partners within the company's internal innovation processes is secured. Although universities and public research institutes are becoming increasingly sought out as strategic innovation partners at global corporations - both at developed and emerging economies - evidence unveils that there are but a handful of companies centred in systematically managing the prospection of external sources for innovation purposes, thus binding the use of these public sources to their strategic innovation objectives (Lauersen & Salter, 2004; Pintec, 2008).

Other authors emphasize that most companies are subject to the consequences that arise from the absence of a strategic direction guiding the search for external partners and of a holistic approach to manage the assortment of sources of innovation (Linder, Jarvenpaa & Davenport, 2003; Lauersen & Salter, 2004; Gomes & Kruglianskas, 2005; Huston & Sakkab, 2006; Chesbrough, 2007, 2012a, 2012b; OECD, 2008; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013).

To this effect, Linder, Javenpaa & Davenport (2003, pp. 43-44) for instance introduce the notion of managing external sources as channels of innovation handling ideas and knowledge ("innovation channels") much the same way one treats the assortment of distribution channels that address end-customers/consumers. This approach beacons the relevance of dealing with the variety of external partners in a differentiated manner given that they are distinct in terms of their very nature, culture and objectives.

This study centres on the concern involving a particular aspect of corporate practices focused on the management of external sources for innovation purposes,

i.e., with the prospection and identification of opportunities to establish R&D+i partnerships with universities and public research institutes. This addresses a portion of a routine that Chatterji (1996) pinpoints in his external innovation sources management model, involving how one may identify and coordinate innovation opportunities via formal and informal external networks (see also Huston & Sakkab, 2006; Chesbrough, 2007, 2012a, 2012b; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Bueno & Balestrin, 2012).

The body of the text herein presents the changes introduced to Natura's innovation strategy with views to mapping competencies and technological opportunities and subsequently seeking partnerships for technological innovation purposes (with universities, research labs, supplying communities and technology-based companies), taking the peculiarities of the Brazilian science, technology and innovation (*CT&I*) environment. This is a change that was coined and implemented with views to, in a strategically oriented manner, directing and supporting the search for external sources of scientific and technological knowledge for innovation purposes.

As a result of this re-orientation of the company's innovation activities, attention is drawn to the setting up of a pioneer and integrated innovation chain (Tuccori, 2009) and to the re-structuring of Natura's technology and innovation unit (R&D+i). This novel alignment leveraged the company into a qualitative leap in terms of innovation strategy focused on the use of biodiversity in cosmetics.

3. METHODOLOGY

This is an exploratory case study with the purpose of elucidating and furthering the comprehension of the studied phenomena in a specific situation, by means of the collection, analysis and interpretation of an assortment of evidences, namely: documents, interviews and observations. The qualitative nature of the study is worthy of special mention since no scientific sampling was inferred and no attempt is made to quantify results obtained but rather, a small group of respondents is bound to the investigation's precision and credibility (Vasconcellos, 2008; Yin, 2001).

In-depth interviews were conducted to unfold the investigation questioning professionals that between the end of the 90's and up to the year of 2009 experienced all the changes the company implemented to manage its technology and innovation unit (R&D+i). The following professionals were heard: a Senior New Cosmetics Technologies Researcher and the company's Innovation Vice-President.

Interviews were conducted in such a manner as to attempt to identify:

1. factors that motivated this openness;
2. difficulties and learnings of this pathway;
3. prime results and advantages of opening the innovation model;
4. how this process might be improved.

To gather primary and secondary information on strategies, business results and technological evolution of the company's products, Natura's sites and official documents were researched.

Special mention ought to be made to the fact that two of this study's authors worked at both managerial and executive levels at Natura's R&D+i unit. One of the authors worked at the company for ten years having followed the implementation and learning processes throughout the structuring and systematization of the company's innovation management processes.

Therefore the analysis also includes experiences authors witnessed and field trips to universities, technology-based companies and supplying communities in Brazil and to Natura's laboratory in France to develop and formally settle partnerships in Europe, alike.

4. NATURA

Natura was founded in 1969 as a cosmetics compounding pharmacy located in the city of São Paulo. The founder spawned learning in the cosmetics arena when purchasing raw materials at the request of a beautician. This professional formulated individually tailored cosmetic solutions to treat each customer's skin. Therefore, at that time, the company's product development strategy shaped in an informal and empirical manner but did focus on the client in a customized manner.

From the start at São Paulo's first store to a regional and subsequently national and international operation, the company chose to rest on a direct sales model which to date is one of its sustainability and growth pillars within the marketplace.

As an open capital company since 2004, Natura is Brazil's largest manufacturer of cosmetics and hygiene and beauty products (taking the cosmetics, perfumery and personal hygiene segments and excluding those devoted to diapers, oral hygiene, hair dyes, nail polish, sanitary pads and others) and tops the direct sales segment. Currently, Natura counts on approximately 7 thousand collaborators and in 2010 reported net revenues amounting to R\$ 6,3 billion. According to the company's 2012 Annual Report, both net revenues and net profits increased 13,5 % and 3,7 % respectively, in comparison to the previous year whilst net profits neared R\$ 861 million.

The company is headquartered at Cajamar (a city on the outskirts of greater São Paulo's metropolitan area, thus within the State of São Paulo) at a site that hosts Latin America's largest integrated manufacturing, logistics and R&D centre. Furthermore, Natura holds operations in the Argentine, Chile, Colombia, Peru, Mexico and in France where it has a store and a research and technology hub. Counting on a sales team comprising approximately 1,5 million consultants whereby over one million address Brazil and approximately 300 thousand the overseas markets, the company sells to almost 100 million consumers (Relatório Anual Natura, 2012, p. 5). In 2012, Natura invested 2.6% of its net revenue in science, technology, innovation and knowledge networks (R\$ 154 million) and launched 104 new products. Special mention ought to be made to the fact that, in 2012, 67.2% of the company's gross revenues derived from products launched during the previous 24 months. (Relatório Anual da Natura, 2012, p. 42).

The company has three R&D centers in Brazil, namely at Cajamar (SP), and in the north of the country, at Benevides (PA) and Manaus (AM) employing some 250 collaborators. The most recent center - known as Nina (Natura Innovation Nucleus Amazônia) - was inaugurated in August, 2012 and as a knowledge hub its mission is to encourage the formation of research networks comprising local, national and international science and technology institutions (Relatório Anual da

Natura, 2012, p. 42). As of 2006, Natura also operates an Advanced Technology Centre in Paris where focus lies in skin research.

The following strategic directives guide the development of the company's technologies, products and concepts (Natura, 2008, p. 12):

1. focus the Brazilian biodiversity as a source of assets and raw materials;
2. generate local community wealth encouraging economically feasible, socially equitable and environmentally correct activities;
3. consolidate the commitment with sustainable development, investing in agro-ecological model knowledge and certification programs that ensure the availability of resources for forthcoming generations;
4. develop and use biodegradable formulations, recycled and recyclable packaging and extend the use of refill technologies;
5. vegetalize products by employing renewable sources and substitute synthetic raw materials for new natural actives and raw materials;
6. ensure optimal product effectiveness and safety by employing methodologies and tests that replace those conducted on animals;
7. conduct scientific studies to build knowledge and substantiate Well Being related benefits;
8. implement the Open Innovation Model to develop and acquire technologies, establishing partnerships with universities and research centres in Brazil and abroad, to generate knowledge and innovation; and ,
9. improve the management of generated knowledge;

Open innovation is a conceptual approach that foresees the implementation of a business model guided by the search and optimal use of partnerships that are external to the company, for innovation purposes. This rests on the fact that according to Chesbrough (2012a, 2012b), not all grand ideas necessarily arise from within the company (open entry model) and nor ought all of the organization's great ideas to mandatorily be internally explored (open output model). Thus, it is this author's understanding that one may interact with the external environment so as to make best use of resources and capabilities, with views to achieving innovation.

As disseminated via the company's institutional documents, "for Natura, innovation is at the core of value creation and permeates in a transversal manner all of the company's strategic pillars" (Relatório Anual Natura, 2011, p. 30, 2012, p. 41). With this vision in mind, as early as back in the 80's despite then having a poorly structured R&D unit, the company invested in the expansion of its product portfolio. The mentioned frailness refers to the fact that at the time, Natura's R&D heavily relied on existing technologies offered by the marketplace and in the technological offer made by suppliers, then hardly having a chance of differentiating itself in the arena and leading innovation in the field of cosmetics, rather standing, in terms of technological strategies, as an "efficient follower". Meanwhile, the company started to operate in other regions of the country such as in the southernmost state of Rio Grande do Sul (Canoas), in the northeast (Jaboatão dos Guararapes - PE) and in other cities of the south-eastern region of Brazil, namely Itapeçerica da Serra in the State of São Paulo and Matias Barbosa, in Minas Gerais. During the 80's these activities characterized Natura's Cycle I of Expansion.

As of the early 90's, the company began to structure its technological function pointing towards its Cycle II of Expansion by choosing sustainable development as a core strategic pillar and by resorting to biodiversity as a source of new ingredients and new technologies coined for use in its products and to this effect laid forth the following guidelines:

- outlining new organizational formats, governance structures and a favourable innovative process environment to ease the flow of knowledge and of information, internal and external (partners) interaction of teams engaged in R&D+i, operations, sales and rulings;
- hiring highly qualified professionals on the marketplace (some with international experience) and specialists with widely acknowledged scientific knowledge (for both R&D technical related areas and those involved with the management of innovation and with external partnerships to attract R&D project proposals) so as to compose the company's internal R&D+i team;
- systematizing practices and formalized routines for innovation management purposes (Vilha, 2009);

- structuring a practice to attract external partners and encourage scientific cooperation with *ICTs*, based on the releasing of calls for bids in conjunction with development agencies (Fapesp – State of São Paulo’s Research Support Foundation, CNPq – National Scientific and Technological Development Council, Finep – Studies and Projects Financing Institution, etc.) for public tenders (sporadic) involving projects of corporate interest (Tuccori, 2009; Ferro, 2010).

As of the 2000’s, the company decided to further “open” the scope of its innovation model, in light of the interest in extending its activities within the cosmetics marketplace via the internationalization process of its activities. The objective was to increase its Latin-American market share and furthermore, enter the European and North-American markets (Ferro, 2010)) and, above all, respond to the need of consolidating its “offensive” technological strategy centred on the development of proprietary technologies, i.e., “proprietary active principles and cosmetic products that differ from those traditionally offered by the market and which offer proven innovative benefits to users” (Tuccori, 2009, p. 14). To this effect, Natura sought to extend the incorporation and participation of potential partners in R&D+*i* centred processes with views to developing solutions along technological pathways that still called for exploration.

From upper management’s standpoint, the mentioned opening with views to incorporating potential partners for innovation purposes would be crucial to ensure the attaining of their objectives of entering new markets, promoting insertion and strengthening Natura’s operations in the international arena. The underlying reason for this approach lay in the fact that the company would have to face traditional players within the local segment (leading multinationals), adjust to international rulings and moreover, conquer a market deemed more demanding than that of Brazil. Therefore, Natura decided to invest in collaborative processes with *ICTs* and technology-based companies to promote the faster development of more consistent technologies and innovations, i.e., with substantive research and innovation content embedded within products, packaging and so forth. It was the company’s understanding that technological collaboration with these partners would enable the reduction of the time interval between launches over the years, shortening development cycles.

To this effect, Natura initiated a flow of “systemic” changes in the R&D+i function with views to extending and strengthening its competencies in proprietary technologies to develop new cosmetics, employing active principles and resources of Brazil’s biodiversity. All in all, during the years 2000, this set of initiatives corner stoned Natura’s Cycle III of Expansion.

This study assesses how these systemic changes were implemented in the field of innovation at Natura and moreover, which challenges and opportunities spruced during this pathway. The intent is to analyze the set of repercussions of such shifts on the company’s R&D+i structure, with the adoption of innovation-oriented partnerships as well as if the adoption of open innovation practices contributed with the acceleration of Natura’s technological innovation processes. As from reports on this experience, objectives include the highlighting of learnings and issues that call for attention during the implementation of an open innovation model, i.e., of a structured model seeking innovation centric technological collaboration with external to the company partners.

5. THE CENTRALITY OF COOPERATION FOR THE ALIGNMENT OF BUSINESS STRATEGY WITH THAT TECHNOLOGICAL

During the 80’s, the new products Natura developed were based on the compounding lab’s expertise and in the collaboration of raw material suppliers. Despite remaining highly dependent of the technological offer made by these suppliers, activities then already evidenced the company’s choice favouring partnerships. Furthermore, Natura did not possess enough critical mass to develop proprietary technologies. This means that the company’s product development was conducted based on existing market-available technologies. Therefore, if on one hand new raw materials, actives and formulations suggested by suppliers of the cosmetic and perfumery industry sustained innovations during that period, on the other, the company remained dependent of technological evolution as available on the market. This technological strategy was characterized by an operating profile of

“efficient follower” and consequently, featured few possibilities of differentiating Natura from competitors and of coming to lead the cosmetic innovation process.

It was only at the end of the 90’s that the company decided to significantly invest in R&D with views to developing proprietary active principles and cosmetic products that posed a difference before those deemed traditional within the market, i.e., which offered innovative benefits to users, namely: well-being and the addressing of problems and needs for the care and maintenance of one’s personal image (according to life stages and the year’s seasons).

During this period, the company consolidated its beliefs, values and *raison d’être*. The company’s strategy – its theory as to how to obtain competitive advantage (Barney & Hesterly, 2008) – began to reflect its choice for commitment with sustainable development and the fostering of “well-being well” (i.e., the individual’s well-being for another’s, emphasizing the relationship, and for the whole - the planet). As of the definition of its very purpose of existence and its strategic objectives, the company’s technological strategy was formulated.

Therefore, based on these drivers, the company set as strategic goal the development of proprietary cosmetic product technologies (of exclusive use) to significantly differentiate itself from its competitors. The objective was to develop scientific ground technologies of safe use and proven (measurable) benefits.

The first initiative was to give start to a process involving the hiring of market stemmed professionals (researchers with international experience at multinational companies) and from the academic arena (science focused researchers). In addition to internalizing these competencies to strengthen the company’s internal R&D team (product development and innovation area) the target was to foster a favourable, diversified environment that might stimulate both new products generation and benefit measurement technologies.

The newly hired specialists contributed with a professional background that included skills in both research project execution and product development project management. This previously acquired professional expertise reinforced the team’s competencies in the two dimensions of the company’s technological innovation process, namely: applied research conducted with scientific rigor; and the development of products and technological innovation conducted with project, resource, budget, plans, goals and deadline management discipline.

On one hand, "Chronos" was the brand name elected to take the lead in the technological education process with views to the development of more efficient active principles and cosmetics. On the other, the brand name "Ekos" was coined with investments in new competencies to develop technologies and products as of Brazil's biodiversity.

The year of 1998 landmarks the start of Natura's partnerships with the launching of a new facial cream ("Chronos" with vitamins A, C and E) developed in joint collaboration with Colética, a company that supplies active principles. This partner developed Vitamin C thalaspheeres enabling the vitamin's stabilizing in the cream's formulation. Meanwhile, another partnership driven initiative kicked off with the narrowing of relations between Natura and a renowned French cosmetic product development consultant. This contact gave rise to a long lasting partnership that contributed both with the technological evolution of the "Chronos" facial treatment product line and with the development of internal skills to develop methodologies and infrastructure to study new actives and measure new skin treatment benefits.

During the following year, 1999, the company hired its new R&D Director from the international market arena and set up a lab focused on the study of advanced concepts for new targets and active principles, known as Advanced Concepts Technology (*TCA*). Gathering scientists from the market and the academic environment, this pre-competitive research centre's objective was to develop proprietary technologies for in-company purposes and thus supply the product development team with new actives and new product launch concepts. Thus, the *TCA*'s technological assignment centred on developing new proven efficient skin treatment active principles and baseline skin functioning mechanism knowledge generation studies. At the time, following the French consultant's advice, Natura settled the first technological development collaboration contract: a partnership with a researcher at the Paris VI University's Faculty of Medicine (Professor Ladislav Robert), specialized in cellular communication and ideator of the biotechnology-based active principle known as "Elastinol". The partnership fruited into the development of a family of the active Elastinol that was to serve as source of skin reconstruction and collagen production in Natura's Chronos' product line. Special mention ought to be made to the fact that Chronos with Elastinol sustained several

technological generations involving this brand name, namely: Elastinol+, Elastinol+R and Chronos Firming Elastinol+R Complex, respectively launched in 2003, 2004 and 2006.

At the end of the 90's whilst developing Natura's flagship product (Chronos) the company invested in a business platform comprising actives and raw materials from Brazil's biodiversity. The purpose was to add value to natural resources and at the same time contribute with conservation and the building of scientific knowledge on the theme. To this effect, investments in new technological platforms had to be made to enable the sustainable prospection and supply of these resources, calling for the coining of a new technological platform to develop and sustain the new business platform, focused on products inspired in the country's biodiversity and its sustainable use.

A land marking event took place in 2001: the inauguration of the new integrated site, at Cajamar (SP) devoted to technological research, development and innovation, manufacturing, logistics and distribution. Another major cornerstone that shaped during this same year was the launch of Chronos Elastinol and the new brand, "Ekos".

The ideation of the Ekos brand name aimed at integrating popular knowledge with that sprung from science once having been inspired by the traditional knowledge of populations that lived in the Amazon Forest and in the use of active principles that prove to offer scientifically evidenced action. Ekos' value proposition was to add value to biodiversity, developing cosmetics and fragrances employing Brazil's natural biodiversity resources, enabling the same's sustainable use and conservation for forthcoming generations.

To launch the first lines of Ekos's active principles – based on the Amazon's plants and fruits – Natura identified partner companies that also believed in the potential posed by biodiversity and willingly bet on the challenge of identifying and organizing supply chains that would stem from supplying communities (rural, waterfront, also known as traditional). Natura's role was to identify the cosmetic potential of the new actives and raw materials offered by Brazilian plants and develop a methodology that would provide evidence of the new raw materials' safety of use and efficiency. Partner companies in turn were in charge of organizing the regular supply of resources, in a sustainable manner. To this effect, they

received support in the form of investments and technical consulting services offered by Natura's internal R&D team specialists.

Ekos was launched almost at the same time that the Provisional Measure (MP) Nr. 2.186/2000 was published, ruling the access and sustainable use of biodiversity in compliance with the Biological Diversity Convention (CDB) that had sprung from ECO-92 (Environment and Development United Nations Conference – CNUMAD) and the signing of the CDB's statement, in 1996. Thus, the new Ekos business platform, so as to be deemed sustainable, also called for new research and knowledge (scientific, technological and traditional) knowledge that did not as yet exist within the company. Therefore, the internal R&D team - which mastered the required skills to develop cosmetic products and actives with conventional principles (synthetic) offered by regular suppliers and also the entire obtaining, measuring and benefit evidencing process - had to be strengthened in fields involving the knowledge of plants: prospection, extraction, isolation of active principles, proof of efficiency and safety of use.

Two actions contributed with the strengthening of Natura's internal R&D team in as much as the assimilation and internalization of R&D competencies centered on biodiversity was concerned: the acquisition of a phytotherapeutic company (Flora Medicinal, located in Rio de Janeiro) and the hiring of new R&D professionals, specialized in Botany.

The challenge lay in incorporating new practices involving the prospection of plant active principles, increasing the supply of new technologies for the development of new products. Furthermore, the sustainable supply process of these plants had to be ruled and paced on an ongoing basis, yet as of small rural communities. Finally, the quest also comprised ensuring legal matters were adequately addressed and that benefits were likewise shared with plant suppliers.

Unlike the innovation chain of companies that are sourced with raw materials that derive from crude oil resources or synthetic production processes, the new R&D focused on biodiversity also comprised organizing the innovation chain involving the cultivation of these species, from plantation and traditional sustainable management routines right through simply ensuring new raw materials were readily made available (for pick-up purposes), at their point of origin.

The new Ekos-centered R&D team had “to” and came “to” incorporate professionals that were anything but conventional at cosmetics industries, namely: biologists, agronomists and forestry engineers. These collaborators possessed focused knowledge in Ethnobotany, Sustainable Plant Production and Certified Forestry Management and were responsible for the prospection and identification of areas and suppliers that offered sustainable management potential for then entirely unknown, new plants as far as the ideation of new actives and cosmetic products was concerned.

On the other hand, the acquisition of Flora Medicinal boosted the development of new plant technologies and active principles. Furthermore, via the scope of relations with this company, new knowledge was acquired (novel to *Natura*) in the field of approval of the use of phytotherapeutic products, in as much as regulatory and *Anvisa* (National Sanitary Surveillance Agency) requirements were concerned, in addition to that pertaining to species traceability.

The combination of this set of efforts positively impacted the development of new end-to-end internal skills, preparing the new integrated R&D team to research from bare origin and plant species production, to the isolation of the active principle and final cosmetic product preparation.

As a result of this re-orientation of the company’s innovation activities, emphasis ought to be placed on the setting up of an unheard-of, integrated and entire innovation chain (Tuccori, 2009; Vilha, 2009), in addition to the restructuring of *Natura*’s R&D and Innovation unit. This shift leveraged the company into a qualitative leap in terms of innovation strategy centred on the use of biodiversity in the field of cosmetics.

6. SCIENTIFIC PARTNERSHIPS

To sustain the demand for new active sustainable plant-sourced active principles and the generation of new cosmetic and phytotherapeutic products, in addition to the partnerships set with raw materials suppliers and the collaboration with rural and traditional communities, another strategy that *Natura* adopted was that of establishing scientific partnerships with *ICTs* (universities and research

institutes). The company chose to invest in tenders that were jointly prepared with fostering agencies for specific calls for bids purposes, with views as to attracting partners for the development of research projects in fields it did not as yet master.

In 2001 for instance, Natura launched a tender for phytotherapeutic products in conjunction with the *CNPq* (National Research Centre) comprising the research, prospection and extraction, analytical methods and standardization of plant active principles that offered phytotherapeutic potential. This tender approved five projects involving the following institutions: *UFMG* – Minas Gerais's Federal University, *USP* – University of São Paulo, *UFC* – Ceará's Federal University, *Unicamp* – Campinas's State University and *Uerj* – Rio de Janeiro's State University.

In 2002 a call for bid was released by the *FINEP*'s (Funding for Studies and Projects) Green-Yellow fund and several partnerships were established with universities across the country.

In 2003, at the opening of the *PITE* (Technological Innovation Partnership Research Support Program) Natura launched a joint tender with *FAPESP* (São Paulo's State Research Foundation) which sought to capture project proposals focused on the Brazilian biodiversity's plant active principles and resources that offered phytotherapeutic and cosmetic application potential. Approximately 50 proposals were turned in, from which 13 projects were approved. Proposal evaluation centered on both scientific quality criteria (assessed by *FAPESP*) and potential application to Naturas' business metrics (assessed by the company itself).

Despite only being occasionally released, tenders resulted in benefits for Natura in as much as establishing a routine that till then was unprecedented in the company's day-to-day was concerned: the narrowing of relations with the academic arena (*ICT* researchers and chief scientists) and with fostering agencies that formulate public policies in the fields of science, technology and innovation - *CT&Is*.

Special mention is herein made to the fact that Natura's experience with tenders calling for research projects for joint development with university researchers preceded the edition of the Innovation Law (Nr. 10.973 of December 2004). Therefore, on one hand, the so-called *NITs* (Technological Innovation Nuclei) at universities had not as yet been ruled (or barely existed) and on the other, there were no specialized professionals at the company to conduct negotiations involving intellectual property matters, for instance.

Not surprisingly, the company experienced a number of difficulties to formally rule its first partnerships, particularly those pertaining to the transfer of funds from projects to the respective proponents, communication channels and dialogue with the institutions. This primarily arose from the fact that those held responsible were not readily found at their workplaces and so, negotiations took far too long. Hardly ever did communication flow without noise. Once negotiations were concluded, some contracts still required almost one year to be settled and even then, issues pertaining to intellectual property could still be subject to *a posteriori* discussion, most often at the end of project execution itself. Mistuning of the kind hindered negotiations for both parties: company and universities. In some cases, during the course of projects, other institutions were involved in the execution of specific project stages, without the company's prior consent or discussion of rights and duties.

During this period, project execution sluggishness, the absence of adequate communication between internal and external researchers, impairments to meet the objectives and goals set at start, difficulties in the tracing of patents (search of prior trademarking) and the protection of technologies developed in conjunction with partners, plus issues pertaining to the sharing of results and of project legacies involving intellectual property and the non-authorized publishing of research findings were the prime challenges faced by Natura and for this very reason, learning opportunities.

It was still in 2003 that a scientific committee was set up to encourage the interchange of knowledge on biodiversity. Comprised by scientists and executives from both Natura and the marketplace, with renown expertise in themes involving phytotherapeutic products and Brazil's biodiversity, the committee's prime responsibility was to criticize and offer advice to Natura's Brazilian biodiversity-centred sustainable technology development strategy.

The very fact that this committee existed helped narrow the gap between the internal R&D team and players that comprised the country's science, technology and innovation system. Closer ties further contributed towards Natura becoming more familiar with the dynamics of the Brazilian *CT&I* environment, extending internal knowledge "about" and benefitting "from" the country's innovation fostering instruments.

University-company interaction was favoured by the interest of Natura's researchers and by that of the universities in promoting the exchange of scientific and technological knowledge, as well as by the interest of the company's upper management in betting on the country's scientific and technological potential and in facing the learning stages (difficulties) during the early days of this interaction. Once closer ties were built and relationship processes defined, partnerships were expected to excel.

7. ORGANIZATION FOR INNOVATION PURPOSES: THE RESTRUCTURING OF NATURA'S R&D+I UNIT

To address market and international expansion growth objectives, in 2005 a technological plan was prepared and implemented. To this effect, once Natura's technological strategy was re-evaluated, a study was conducted to define how to strengthen the company's R&D area. Benchmarking exercises, analysis of the R&D and innovation structure of innovative local and international companies were also conducted. Furthermore, on site visits were paid to companies that operate in the hygiene and cosmetics segment (one of which was at Procter and Gamble), as well as companies of the Information Technology and Communication (*TIC*) segment.

The practical result of this study was the preparation of a Technological Development Plan ground on two strategies: invest in the strengthening of the internal R&D unit and open the company's innovation model.

A strengthened internal R&D unit was viable once the level of investments was maintained at approximately 3% of net sales revenues. This percentage ensured resources for the updating of the technological infrastructure centred on Research and Technology (*R&T*) and for the continued education of professionals to the extent that at least 50% of the internal R&D team remained made up of post-graduated professionals.

The systematic adoption of the open innovation model combining internal and external ideas to coin technology and innovation projects sought to enable the acceleration of the company's ability to generate new technologies and radical innovations so as to spruce new businesses.

One of the core corporate innovation management maturity dimensions corresponds to the ability a company evidences in exploring its resources and capabilities – valuable, rare, barely imitable (Barney & Hesterly, 2008) – in addition to the proven ability to systemize processes and offer structured, integrated tools to manage innovation process related decision making flows (Quadros & Vilha, 2006; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008; Carvalho, Santos & Barros Neto, 2011, 2013).

Thus, from a formal innovation-oriented structure standpoint, some changes were deemed relevant and to this effect, three executive functional units lead by Directors were introduced, namely:

1. Research and Technology Unit: commissioned to seek radical innovation so that research coined possibilities, generating competitive advantage in as much as the production of knowledge was concerned, reinforcing the company's choice to further knowledge in Brazil's biodiversity and its sustainable use in product formulations (Natura, 2008, p. 17);
2. Products and Packaging Development Unit: maintained and developed the product portfolio, generating differentiated competitive value via products and packaging. Closely linked with the marketing function, the unit employed both in-company and via scientific partnerships developed technologies and/or those of market and/or supplier developed origin (Natura, 2008, p. 18);
3. Technical Services Unit: present in research and development processes, supported and provided support to technical and administrative issues such as the regularizing of the company and its products within the purview of the local and international sanitary and environmental rulings; raw-material, packaging material, finished product and so forth specifications. (Natura, 2008, p. 21).

Despite being functionally separate, the three units were integrated via processes that were specially designed to ensure agility and speed at times of new technology and product development, addressing both the domestic and international markets.

The Technical Services Unit's was foremost ideated to treat matters pertaining to international regulation. Within the scope of its value proposition, it

would further be held accountable for developing regulation intelligence activities. The underlying reason for this assignment rest in the fact that to address Natura´s intended internationalization process, understanding the requirements of the countries that would nest the company´s new commercial operations was deemed vital. The unit was also held accountable for treating matters pertaining to biodiversity access and related traditional knowledge, in compliance with each country that was of Natura´s potential commercial interest´s legislation.

Serving the purpose of core axis ensuring the success of the company´s innovation process, in addition to integration of the three technical units, Natura also secured integration with the business and marketing areas. To this effect, an Innovation Vice-Presidency was structured and solely commissioned to manage the company´s innovation process. This new configuration within the formal organization – placing innovation at the top of the organizational pyramid, ensuring it directly reported to the company´s Chief Executive Officer – defined the standing of the field of innovation within Natura´s identity and power structure. Thereafter, the company´s upper management and leadership would formally be involved in the in the governance and innovation management process.

The company began to manage is innovation process in a systemic and aligned with its competitive strategy manner, structuring and formalizing crucial to innovation management practices (Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008). Thus, the operation of these units came under the monitoring of “technology projects funnels” and “new, undergoing development, product funnels” management committees that gathered on a weekly and fortnightly basis.

To ensure strategic alignment and the effective implementation of technology and development projects, Natura started to use decision making tools such as stage gates (Cooper, Edgett & Kleinschmidt, 2002a, 2002b) and innovation funnels (Clark & Wheelwright, 1993; Gavira, Ferro, Rohrich & Quadros, 2007).

Project management started to be operationalized at two aligned processes, research (*R*) and development (*D*) management: the technology and the innovation funnels, respectively. The technology funnel – of long term and high risk – corresponded to a set of processes that identified, researched and developed new raw materials and resources (particularly those stemming from biodiversity), in addition to new packaging materials and technologies, non-invasive methodologies

for the purpose of efficiency demonstration and product safety (alternative tests to those performed on animals), objective evidencing of well-being and environmental impact methodologies. The innovation funnel – of short term, lower risk and clear cut projects – included the new concepts and products development processes as of mapped market needs (Natura, 2008, p. 22).

Figure 1: Technological innovation strategic management tools

Source: Adapted as of Natura (2008)

Technologies and knowledge generated throughout the first funnel (whether internally developed or obtained via external partnerships) input cosmetic treatment products, packaging and services ideated as a result of the second funnel. The figure thus illustrates that cooperation with Natura preferably took place along the first funnel. Each of these funnels would come to be managed according to the state-gates approach, comprising specific phases and criteria for project progress approval purposes. Once at the technology funnel, projects were assessed across four gates whilst that devoted to innovation subjected projects to five assessment gates.

The company improved its internal processes in 2012 so as to integrate all innovation initiatives and speed the innovation pace. One major measure to this effect was the setting up of the Innovation Nucleus where the core objective was to reduce the time lapse between the springing of ideas and the shaping of a product or service concept, favouring the identification of opportunities at any corporate front (Relatório Anual da Natura, 2012).

8. ORGANIZATION FOR COOPERATION PURPOSES: THE CREATION AND STRUCTURING OF AN EXCLUSIVE PARTNERSHIPS AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION-ORIENTED MANAGEMENT

Collective learnings resultant from relationships with those *ICTs* that obtained approval of projects within the scope of *CNPq*, *FINEP* and *FAPESP* tenders were core to Natura's taking of a decisive step towards structuring and systemizing technological collaboration devoted routines and tools, particularly since learnings unveiled opportunities to improve the technological innovation partnership process itself. Furthermore, the very approval of the Innovation Law in 2004 also contributed with the fostering of new investments coming to be allotted to the R&D unit.

Therefore, the company smartly articulated learnings gathered during the mentioned process with current public policies ruling science, technology and innovation. To this effect, in 2006 Natura set up a unit devoted to the capturing, development and management of new partnerships with academic and corporate institutions: Partnerships and Technological Innovation Management.

This area arose within the company's power structure and thus came to directly report to the Research and Technology Director (see Figure 2 that follows). This coins an element that bears relevant meanings. On one hand, it reflects the adoption of a new formalized organizational configuration that enabled the implementation of the assignment's strategy. On the other, it reflects the company's overall strategy evidencing Natura's intent to adopt organized practices in alignment "with" and consistent "with" its corporate strategy and that pertaining to innovation. The structure would come to have a strong correlation with the

company's corporate strategy, following the same. Structure and strategy (and managerial choices) mutually intertwined, resulting in an innovative configuration to ensure innovation (Chandler Jr., 1987; Chandler Jr. & Daems, 1994).

Figure 2: Natura's technology and innovation organizational structure

Source: Natura's Campus Portal (n.d.)

This unit's dynamics would have to comply with the Triple Helix Network and Partnerships Model (Etkowitz, 2008) whereby each player accounts for its own role, namely: the government contributed with public policies encouraging innovation and funding, such as coordination and public policy execution (educational, technological, industrial, etc.), agent incentives, entrepreneurship incentives, innovation policies, fostering and funding programs, corner-stoning of regulatory frameworks,

sustaining of a favourable macro-economic environment and provisioning of adequate infrastructure. *ICTs* contributed with the generation of new knowledge and education of qualified human resources, via basic and applied research, prototype development, knowledge generation and dissemination, training and private sector technology transfer. Private companies in turn collaborated with applied research, the creation of technological innovation, the transformation of knowledge into goods and services, in addition to the development, production, sale and dissemination of technologies. At Natura, a fourth helix emerged: Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's) specialized in sustainable development. Core to Natura's partnerships process, these NGOs contributed with project management support involving rural communities and materials recycling, as well as with the transfer of technology to the civil society.

Ideated to consolidate the opening of Natura's innovation model mediating the company's relations with its internal R&D team and with external partners (suppliers, scientific community, traditional communities and NGOs), this unit became a core element and posed strategic significance in the innovation partner's management process. The company re-structured its Innovation area, organized itself to efficiently explore its resources and capabilities and proposed to open its business model to subsequently consolidate its open innovation model via the creation of the Partnerships Management area.

In addition to setting this area up, other initiatives were also undertaken to strengthen Natura's innovation partnership-based model such as the coming together of Natura Innovation and Technology, *Orsa Florestal* and *Centroflora* to set up *Ybios* – an “antenna” company coined to capture research and technological development – and the subsequent setting up of a skin and *in vitro* studies and test lab in Paris (France) to attract new partnerships with European specialists and still, a vegetable oils study laboratory in the north of the country (Belém- PA) with views to coming into close contact with knowledge on Amazonian oilseeds.

The creation of a unit focused on the capturing and management of partnerships represented the acknowledgement of the need to educate professionals with expertise on the peculiarities of Brazil's science, technology and innovation environment and of the fostering instruments addressing the cooperation between *ICTs* and companies. Thus, the Partnerships and Technological Innovation

Management's mission was to implement a structured, periodic and systemized process to capture new projects and to this effect these flowed in on a continuous basis (and no longer sporadically as was till then the case via tenders launched in conjunction with the State Research Support Foundations – FAPs) and were to be developed in partnership with the *ICTs* and foremost, had to be aligned with the company's strategic-technological plan.

Professionals were selected and trained in negotiation skills, diverse culture player relationship management, *ICT* dialogue and simultaneously in the company's technological and innovation strategic vision. This group of collaborators were also expected to be proficient in assessing and prioritizing new partnerships and projects (according to impact and potential commercial return of investments made in new technologies) and still, be skilled in counselling in-company technical leaders as to best project and partner options.

Four actions undertaken by the Partnerships Management area were core to the progress of the partnership model with *ICTs*. The first was the formalization and approval of a new technological collaboration partnership relationship policy which not only established the company's standing in terms of minimum relationship conditions so as to align expectations and needs as of partnership start, but also defined the sharing of results arrangement modes. This partnership relationship policy set, for instance, the grounds for negotiations of matters involving confidentiality, intellectual property co-ownership, technology valuation according to its impact on the business and exclusive use compensation, licensing opportunities involving other businesses as well as partnership management aspects. Special mention is made to the fact that systematization and formalization of this policy was one of the fruits that arose from learnings acquired from the relationship with partners captured via tenders. The underlying reason for this rests in the fact that, at the time, it was not as yet clear how research results ought to be shared in as much as publication, compensation for the use of technologies or even intellectual property protection were concerned.

The second action comprised the construction of a strategic management model "of" and "for" cooperation with *ICTs*: the Natura Technological Innovation Campus Program, in conjunction with the setting up of a portal for on-line, continuous inflow capturing of proposals for new projects and partners. Natura's

Campus Program (set up in 2001 via *FAPs*' coupled tenders) was re-structured and systematized to encourage the capturing of long term partnerships, aligned with the company's technological platforms. The point of counting on a continuously flowing program to capture partnerships and projects was support the company's non-dependence on occasional fostering tenders for partner attraction purposes.

Both the setting up of this portal (to disseminate and capture R&D+i proposals) and of the Scientific Committee (to follow-up new academic and entrepreneurial proposals) contributed with ensuring greater participation of joint projects at the company's technology funnel. In addition to having generated more consistent (relevant) innovations in terms of technologies for its products, the company reports having, by 2008, already managed to count on 50% participation of externally sprung projects, a figure that comprised 2010's targets (Natura, 2008).

The third initiative was the coining of processes to manage and follow-up partnerships - ideated well beyond mere technical matters - taking into account the new project analysis and selection dimensions, within the new partnership capturing and management processes. Thus, strategic project selection criteria were introduced into the same, amongst which: project and partnership management, technical-financial project monitoring, partnership relationship, proposal technological and innovative potential assessment, partnership long term (and not only short term) results potential assessment.

The fourth action was the ideation of processes to capture and manage R&D project funding. The partnership with *ICTs* development process also took into account the assortment of innovation funding mechanisms offered by fostering agencies and the encouragement of its use. To optimize resorting to the same, Natura invested in professionalizing the funding area with views to handling fostering matters. Thus, professionals chosen to come to be held accountable for the relationship with fostering organizations were trained to coordinate multi-functional teams. These in turn comprised professionals from Natura's finance, fiscal and legal areas. Training also included shaping an integrated vision of each innovation financing mechanism's demands and opportunities; make the use of *FINEP*'S and *BNDES*'s (National Economic and Social Development Bank) financing

lines, of “Good Law” incentives and of the participation in economic subsidy tenders for companies and the hiring of researchers, viable.

As of 2011 the Natura Campus Program progressed into a more open business model format. Launched on the 30th of November at the company’s own portal this on-line program (<http://www.naturacampus.com.br/>) was reformulated and extended to facilitate and broaden the scope of collaborative and network-ground innovation with ICTs in Brazil and abroad. Given the use of interactivity (via the internet and social networks) and the diversification of network-based knowledge construction means, the Program’s most relevant characteristic thus became constant interactivity-based relationships.

The Program began to comprise all fields of knowledge including biology, physics and chemistry and applied humanities and social sciences. Furthermore, it also expanded its scope territory-wise, focusing on the education and strengthening of collaboration networks in Brazil and abroad.

The reason Natura invested in this evolution lay in the capturing of radical innovation project proposals objective and so, the attraction and capturing of partners shaped into two distinct modalities: Calls for Projects and Natura Innovation Challenges.

Calls for Projects are to date opportunities that are periodically opened for the receipt of research project proposals. This model allows for the planning of Natura’s and its partner’s research activities in addition to favouring the comparative analysis of proposals. Proposals addressing Natura’s fields of science are submitted twice a year. During two periods of the year, proposals aligned with Natura’s fields of science are submitted.

In turn, Natura’s Innovation Challenges are still currently launched at Natura’s Campus Portal with the objective of presenting scientific, technical, creative or infrastructural needs, amongst others, covering themes that are of the company’s specific interest. Each challenge has its own set of rules according to the nature of the demand and enables distinct interaction modalities, including concept ideation and creation, collaborative research, co-development, technology transfer and specific awards projects.

In addition to these two new partner recruiting and selection modes, the Natura Campus Program uses an assortment of tools to interact with the scientific

community. The core element of such tools is the connection and interaction between researchers and the dissemination of information across the network. The objective is to ease the identification of mutually beneficent opportunities and the generation of multiple value modalities for the entire network of partners. Some of the company's proposed interaction mechanisms include:

- a. Natura Campus Portal: prime communication channel and relationship link between Natura and its network innovation partners. Content is updated on a regular basis featuring information on science, technology and innovation. The portal hosts blogs and communication tools to enhance interactivity and the articulation of researchers with both Natura and the network as a whole. It also offers access to the Program's Relationship Schedule, featuring relevant events and activities that both Natura and its partners plan to conduct. This tool's purpose is to disseminate the innovation culture and serve as a channel to further extend the reach of reported activities so as to address the assortment of interested audiences;
- b. Thematic blogs: the Natura Campus Portal shelters four blogs focused on four scientific themes within the company's scope of operations, namely: 1. Classic and Advanced Skin and Hair Sciences; 2. Sustainable Technologies; 3. Well-Being and Relations Sciences; and 4. Senses, Design and Experiences. Each blog has a curator who is responsible for the postings and participant debate mediation which can include current Natura partners in addition to new network participants who express interest in the themes;
- c. Newsletters: periodically sent to all of those interested in following up on Natura's fields of operations in as much as scientific and technological advances are concerned. It covers the latest trends and debates in these fields, Natura's perception of the respective trends and the opportunities envisioned to progress collaborative network activities, in a summarized format;
- d. Media Centre: a channel that disseminates information on innovation at Natura: company information, concluded research and case studies and

- other information deemed of relevance for corporate learning sharing purposes and which favour the conduction of new research;
- e. Social networks: the Natura Campus Program is also interconnected with other internet-based social networks (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.), multiplying innovation-related facts and opportunities to demonstrate the importance of collaboration. Information is generated as of a structured and content-safe process;
 - f. Interaction workshops: Natura's Campus Program conducts joint events with *ICTs* to enable the interaction between Natura's researchers and those of these organizations. They are knowledge and experience exchange opportunities which also serve the purpose of identifying common interests that pose scientific and technological research collaboration potential. These workshops are conducted at Natura, at the *ICTs* or even virtually resorting to electronic tool support (YouTube, Vímeo, SlideShare, etc.).

7. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The external environment takes on a relevant role driving in-company changes. Nevertheless, when organizing itself for innovation purposes, elements such as the company's culture (Barbosa, 2002; Vargas, 2008), strategic and managerial choices (Morgan, 1996) and institutional (Powell & DiMaggio, 1991) and regulatory aspects are no less important in the change perception, guidance, negotiation and validation process.

Some classic scholars specifically address the issue of how structure might be related in an intertwined manner with strategy, technology and innovation, including Burns & Stalker (1961), Lawrence & Lorsch (1973), Woodward (1977), Chandler Jr.(1987) and Chandler Jr. & Daems (1994). Contemporary authors such as Huston and Sakkab (2006), Chesbrough (2007) and Tidd, Bessant and Pavitt (2008) advocate that to excel in an increasingly globally competitive environment,

companies would have to develop and learn (to learn) with an innovative work culture and structure. The underlying reason for this statement rests in the fact that with the ever more rapid shortening of product life cycles, they'd have to innovate more often and develop products and/or services in a more efficient manner. Furthermore, given the fact that products and processes are becoming increasingly more complex (multi-technology) one notices that costs and risks to innovate have expanded, raising uncertainty and pressure on research and development (R&D) budgets, whilst, at the same time – given the raise in the complexification of knowledge – the need for interdisciplinarity via cooperation has also become evident (OECD, 2008).

Thus, within the described scenario of inflections and heightened business related uncertainties, a possible arrangement that scholars suggest involves the design of organized configurations based on technological cooperation. One of the approaches that has captured the spotlight over the past few years is that known as open innovation (for definition and details on this concept, see Chesbrough (2012a, 2012b)). Other additional approaches focus on the re-designing of organizational arrangements with views to promoting and coordinating efforts involving corporate collaborative practices have likewise been suggested by Von Hippel (2005) and Eriksson, Niitamo, Kulkki and Hribernik (n.d.), namely: user-oriented innovation and user-driven innovation and living labs, respectively. Tidd, Bessant and Pavitt (2008) also systemized a set of organized arrangements for innovation and learning purposes based on an assortment of possible forms of alliances.

One of the hypothesis raised by authors is that within this environment spangled by contingencies of market and technology shift conditions – thus enhancing complexity, uncertainty, heterogeneity and unpredictability – organizations would shed bureaucratic and mechanic structures to take on organic organizational formats by adopting more open and flexible management structures (Burns & Stalker, 1961; Lawrence & Lorsch, 1973; Morgan, 1996; Lam, 2005; Chesbrough, 2007; OECD, 2008). Of fluid nature, arrangements of the kind would be able to respond in a rapid and innovative manner to this scenarios' requirements, promoting interaction and learning amongst network participants (both internal and external to the company), easing both inter-communication and the organizational change and adjustment process to the same and furthermore, the decision making

process as a whole (Huston & Sakkab, 2006; Chesbrough, 2007; Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008).

If, in Brazil on one hand and in particular as of the enforcement of the Innovation Law – whose spirit is to nurture a favourable and dynamic environment encouraging innovation, overcoming institutional bottlenecks to public-private cooperation in science, technology and innovation so as to ease inter-institution cooperation – the theme of cooperation has often been at the core of debates; on the other, Pintec's (2008) latest data still suggest companies are skittish when it comes to setting cooperative relations with other companies or institutes. Pintec (2008, p. 23) defines cooperation as being "active corporate participation in joint R&D and other innovation projects with another organization (company or institution)".

From 2006 to 2008, the time frame Pintec surveyed and in course when findings herein were reported, industrial companies featured greater cooperation in as much as process innovations (83,4%) are concerned and the most relevant partners for the forming of cooperative relations were their suppliers (65,3%) and clients or consumers (45,3%). Companies still keep their black-box sealed when the subject matter is product innovation, particularly because in 84, 2% of surveyed cases, the company itself is the prime player in the development of the implemented product innovation.

In as much as Natura is concerned, some elements were core to the evolution of its R&D+i and the company's technological cooperation model. Foremost, the determination and involvement of the Founding Presidents and higher executives in the innovation process and still, how the company organized itself to explore its resources and capabilities, hauling innovation to the top of the organizational pyramid (Innovation Vice-Presidency). To this effect, technological collaboration was thus not deemed as an isolated initiative of a Director, Manager or department but rather called for a top-down strategy, namely, in the form of upper management's support and commitment (Huston & Sakkab, 2006). In addition, other changes in the company's structure were conducted with the creation and integration of directorships and the systematizing of organizational practices (such as the Scientific Committee) with views to preparing Natura for collaborative innovation.

It is also worth noting that Natura's R&D area evolved in alignment with the company's business strategy within a systemic mutual interaction process involving businesses' and technological strategies. Another important element was the company's ability to cooperate and develop its partners for innovation purposes. This is a skill that can be learnt and consequently, internalized, reinforced and monitored. From the early stages of its business, one notices that the company is willing to work in a collaborative manner. Foremost, dialogue and the openness to share learnings with internal and external partners were vital elements to ensure the opening of the innovation process at Natura.

The first projects conducted with *ICTs* unveiled a powerful academic bias and lacked industrial applicability. Final product technology use stages and industrial scaling were not taken into account when planning research, hindering the practical use of project outcomes.

The introduction of scientific partnerships at Natura was fruitful in terms of promoting the narrowing of relations between company researchers and academic scientists and to the internalizing of skills within both the company and at the *ICTs*. On one hand, this proximity favoured science-based education of the company's internal R&D team and on the other, the transfer of corporate environment practices to academic researchers. For instance, mentioned practices, include: research planning comprising industry needs and requirements, development of a strategic business vision centred on the discovery of potential application at the marketplace of research findings and finally, project management.

According to Quadros (2008) the implementation of a consistent technological cooperation model calls for a set of managerial competencies, namely: project team leadership, contract negotiation and knowledge of the research business. In as much as roles played by leadership are concerned, one of the key elements resides in the internal R&D team's awareness as to remaining receptive to that which was not internally ideated or produced (in contrast with the "not invented here" syndrome). As per interviewee reports, during its early stages, the innovation partnership model spruced internal researcher resistance, posing difficulties for both project management and monitoring before partners. The team perceived the collaboration movement as a step towards the outsourcing of the R&D function and still, as potential loss of internal competencies.

Thus, the model was apparently far more appreciated by upper executive management than by the operational team and Natura set out to strengthen the internal R&D+i projects research team with training centred on: external partnership management education; in (external) project management information systems; in skills to understand the existing cultural differences between companies universities and in project monitoring processes.

During the model's early stages and in an attempt to leverage new projects and ideas for innovation purposes, projects involving external partnerships kicked off but were not then aligned with the company's technological strategy. Thus an important learning was the setting up of a process to define what was deemed strategic or core to the company and was to be internalized, versus that which could be conducted in a cooperative manner. This also clearly laid forth the partnership development approach: if basic research acquisition (knowledge containing science and fundamentals expertise), if development of applied technologies or if development of consumer final products. Thereafter, the company was in a position to define the partnership portfolio whether projects were set up with academic or corporate partners.

The crucial element to materialize technological collaboration-oriented coordinated actions at Natura was the creation of an exclusive area with a team of professionals devoted to the capturing and management of external partners. This unit was coined with an external partner dialogue and negotiator mandate in addition to that of safeguarding the partnership and monitoring deadlines and results management policies and good practices.

The managerial competencies this unit's professional's learnt and practiced were key success factors. Provisioned by the company via training courses, these skills came to include an integrated vision of the business so as to translate business strategies into technological strategies, ensuring an aligned external partnership portfolio; contract negotiation; project and external partnership management and knowledge in the research business itself. The latter is understood as being a set of data, information, knowledge and peculiarities of Brazil's science, technology and innovation system (and of countries where the company holds or intends to have commercial operations) in terms of instruments, sources and

financing programs; science, technology and innovation indicators and intellectual property management.

It is precisely this set of competencies that shape a characteristic that is akin to a second nature or as pinpointed by Tidd, Bessant and Pavitt (2008, p.100), “the way things are done here” (at our company), which, once learnt, internalized and reinforced become automatic responses to given situations, thus ensuring the very feasibility of innovation-oriented collaboration.

Technological collaboration also demands organizational routines and technological means to promote and structure - in a systemized manner - its very implementation. In other words, tools that put the collaboration-based innovation strategy, into effective practice (Huston & Sakkab, 2006). The portal system that Natura coined likewise shaped into an efficient mechanism for new innovation projects ideas and proposals continued flow capturing purposes.

Finally, at times of technological cooperation model implementation, some points are worth highlighting. First of all, the definition of technological cooperation priorities according to strategic criteria is core to ensure a new projects partnership portfolio arises in full alignment with the company’s technological demands and shortages. At Natura for instance, external innovation partner mapping and prospection preferably target search efforts to secure participation at the company’s technology funnel with views to narrowing potential gaps and strengthening technological areas that the company does not as yet fully master.

In addition to the systemized search for external partners another alternative to infuse the new technologies and products portfolio is to secure technology surveillance activities monitoring open innovation networks (amongst which InnoCentive.com, NineSigma.com, Yet2.com and yourEncore.com); and at technological “antenna” institutes (such as the Innovation Institute or *Inventta* in Brazil and/or international equivalents) that mediate the commercialization of technologies, innovation and intellectual property.

Corporate partnerships can be strengthened at the businesses’ pre-competitive stage via flexible arrangements such as research networks or consortiums. The later most often comprise joint activities focused on a fully pinpointed project (usually involving basic research) which seek to share research

infrastructure, costs and risks and are financed via agreements settled between companies, universities, research institutes and *FAPs* (Tidd, Bessant & Pavitt, 2008).

It is vital to invest in specific training so as to develop multifunctional skills within the company's team of R&D+i professionals (researchers and managers), namely: institutional science, technology and innovation environment monitoring; competitive intelligence; technological and market prospection; technological and new product portfolio management; technological intellectual property, acquisition and licensing; negotiation; supplier, client and research institution cooperation management; technology and new product development project management; innovative organization's strategy, governance, structure and people management; innovation projects financing, incentives and innovation fostering and leveraging government funds; and innovation process assessment.

One might also take into account the use of obsolete and/or no longer of corporate interest technology licensing practices since these may still bear relevance to other markets or organizational contexts.

Likewise, the potential use of venture capital models to finance spin-offs or start-ups that offer potential to contribute with the company's value and innovation chain, according to its market and segment of operations, ought to be pondered. When it comes to companies like Natura, devoted to the cosmetics market, an example of the mentioned possibility would be the financing of technology based companies to operate in the development of new raw materials and materials in Brazil, according to the company's focus on biodiversity and sustainability.

Finally, it's worth exploring the use of opportunities one finds in favourable environments such as at technology parks, to expand the company's technological infrastructure, enabling greater fostering of new ideas given closer contact with basic research environments.

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